

Spatial modelling of morphological phenomena with taxonomic relationships using sub-optimal datasets

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Summary

This paper has two main contributions: first, we describe a framework for spatial modelling of morphological phenomena with taxonomic relationships using sub-optimal datasets. Second, we apply it to our case study area in Central Europe, in order to train models that can expand the original urban classification in new contexts - countries, continents and places with missing data.

KEYWORDS: Urban morphology, spatial modelling, prediction, cities

1 Introduction

Numerous phenomena of interest in the social sciences have an inherent spatial dimension. Modelling and analysing these requires an expanded analytics toolkit to deal with the additional complexity and problems. One of the most important aspects to be taken into account when modelling such phenomena is that of spatial scale. The level of spatial aggregation and disaggregation affects the results of the analysis and relationships between various phenomena (Openshaw, 1983). Similarly, spatial leakage needs to be taken into account when developing predictive spatial models (Fleischmann and Arribas-Bel, 2024). If the phenomenon under analysis exhibits spatial patterns, but the training and testing data is not spatially stratified, there is information leaking from the testing into the training datasets and the reported accuracies tend to be higher than in reality. In this paper we analyse how spatial leakage affects predictive models at different scales, in the context of urban morphology.

Quantitative Urban Morphology is a multidisciplinary field of study which covers aspects of geography, urban planning and data science and aims to describe and classify the physical form of cities based on measurements of their constituent elements - buildings, plots, streets and their configurations at different scales. These approaches can differentiate between parts of cities in which the buildings form large interconnected blocks, typically associated with historical centres, dense

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isolated buildings within a dense street network, large scale isolated building within a sparse street network, such as large modernist housing estates, and others. These developments open up the possibility of a more systematic and comprehensive approach to planning and urban research, which in turn can drive our understanding of cities (Calafiore et al., 2023).

Figure 1 shows the results of Fleischmann et al. (2025) and how the urban morphological classes exist in a taxonomic relationship to each other.

A drawback of this and similar approaches is the strict requirement for high quality data. Fleischmann et al. (2025) or Arribas-Bel and Fleischmann (2022) use building polygons from the respective municipal and national mapping agencies. However, such data is not generally available even for most high-income countries.

An alternative to this cadastre data is voluntary data sources such as OpenStreetMap (OpenStreetMap contributors, 2017), satellite-derived building footprints or aggregators of the two such as OvertureMaps data (Overture Maps Foundation, 2025). Satellite-derived building footprints, such as Microsoft (Microsoft, 2025) or Google Open Buildings (Sirko et al., 2021), have a global scope and are updated frequently. However, these datasets do not come without issues related to heterogeneity and quality.

In this paper, we predict the level 4 classes from Fleischmann et al. (2025), using datasets which are external and of worse quality than the original data - Overture Maps and Microsoft Building Footprints. The study area for the paper covers multiple countries - Poland, Austria, Czechia, Germany and Slovakia, i.e. Central Europe. Furthermore, we make use of the taxonomic relationship between classes to further contextualise the results of the predictive models.

2 Data

There are four core datasets used in the paper - OvertureMaps Street Network, Overture Maps Buildings, Microsoft Building footprints and the classification of urban fabric in central Europe.

Figure 2 shows a visual comparison between the cadastre level data used for the original analysis, and the two datasets we use in this paper. As can be seen from the image, satellite building footprints data is of generally lower quality, while Overture can be of similar quality if it relies on Open Streetmap Data. However, there are additional and missing building footprints that come from different sources, so the cadastre and overture data is not the same.

3 Methods

The methodology in the paper has four stages and is represented in Figure 3.

In the first stage, morphological elements and their characteristics are calculated using Microsoft building, OvertureMaps building footprints and Overture Maps Transportation data. These elements are the predictor variables that the models will use. To achieve this, we develop a highly-scalable polygon and street data pipeline, capable of calculating a list of 60 morphometric characteristics following the approach of Fleischmann et al. (2025). In the second stage, each building used

Figure 1: Taxonomy, which represents the final target labels

Figure 2: Comparison between the data from which the ground truth comes and the sub-optimal datasets

Figure 3: Overview of methodology

in the first stage is assigned a target classification label based on spatial overlap with morphological elements from (Fleischmann et al., 2025), examples of which can be seen in Figure 1.

Third, the data from each source is then split into seven training and testing configurations for the prediction models training and testing. This is summarised in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Trained models per dataset

Five sets that cover every country and every combination of the other four countries are used as test and training data respectively. One set uses random 80/20 splits for train and test data. And lastly, a spatial 80/20 split ensures that training data and testing data are in separate geographical regions. The last step is the analysis of the results from the different modeling configurations for each dataset. In total we analyse the results from 14 models, seven train/test configurations for each of the two datasets. These experiments cover tens of millions of building footprints and streets, and give detailed information about the heterogeneity of urban form in the study area at multiple scales. Our training and testing setup emphasises evaluating the model’s ability to deal with realistic scenarios and with previously unseen data and new urban fabric types.

All stages are carried out independently for the Microsoft Satellite-derived building footprints and for the OvertureMaps data.

The implementation relied on open source tools - momepy, pysal and scikit-learn (Fleischmann, 2019; Pedregosa et al., 2011).

4 Results

Table 1 shows the aggregate weighted, micro and macro F1 scores for all 14 models. The F1 score is the harmonic mean of precision and recall. The higher the value, the better the models perform. The Macro F1 score computes the F1 score per class and takes the average, the weighted F1 score weights the class F1 scores based on the number of observations, while the micro score is a global

one. The Out of Sample, or OoS column shows the average for the models tested on individual countries.

Table 1: Overall F1 scores

(a) Microsoft building footprints								
	Random	Spatial	OoS	SK	PL	DE	AT	CZ
Weighted F1	0.60	0.60	0.51	0.49	0.60	0.49	0.51	0.45
Micro F1	0.58	0.58	0.49	0.47	0.61	0.45	0.49	0.44
Macro F1	0.50	0.49	0.42	0.39	0.48	0.41	0.41	0.39

(b) Overture building footprints								
	Random	Spatial	OoS	SK	PL	DE	AT	CZ
Weighted F1	0.62	0.61	0.53	0.48	0.60	0.56	0.53	0.48
Micro F1	0.60	0.60	0.52	0.46	0.61	0.53	0.52	0.48
Macro F1	0.56	0.56	0.48	0.45	0.53	0.49	0.47	0.46

The weighted and micro F1 scores for the random and spatial models are relatively equal, however the macro F1 score is higher for the models trained on the Overture data. This shows the Overture models are more capable of inferring less numerous classes.

Furthermore, the OoS average and all country models have lower or equal scores than the random and the spatial split model. The spatial split is sometimes slightly lower than the random split, showing that there is some local spatial leakage present. However, the out of sample model and the country models themselves, are consistently lower which shows that there is larger scale spatial leakage happening in the model training. Ultimately, this shows that national planning and economic regimes affect urban morphology in complex ways. It also shows that more complex and reflective of the underlying phenomena testing splits result in more realistic model evaluations for both sub-tables.

Next, we provide the confusion matrix and example predictions for the model trained using a spatial split on Overture data, since it covers the full study area.

Qualitatively, the example predictions in Figure 5 show that first, the models in general do not predict random classes; second, nearby buildings have similar urban classes; and that models capture boundaries between classes. To validate this, and to further explore the result, we analyse the confusion matrix for all the test data for the spatial model.

The confusion matrix in Figure 6 shows quantitative f1 scores for individual classes and ordered such that classes nearer in the taxonomy are closer to each other row-wise. Therefore diagonal misclassifications to nearer classes suggest that at higher levels of the taxonomy, the misclassification will not happen and the overall accuracy will be higher at higher cut off values. This holds true five out of the eight classes. The exceptions are Incoherent Large-Scale Heterogeneous Fabric, Incoherent Large-Scale Homogeneous Fabric and Coherent Dense Adjacent Fabric. In these three

Figure 5: Predictions for example cities

cases the misclassifications happen across different branches in the taxonomy, suggesting again that these are the hardest classes to predict.

Figure 6: Confusion matrix for the spatial model. Normalized by the True Label (row-wise)

5 Conclusion & Discussion

We draw three conclusions from the results.

First, there is a complex relationship between spatial leakage and scale when training predictive models for urban morphological applications. The results show that experimenting with different scales of spatial stratification, gives a more realistic model performance estimates.

Second, taxonomic relationships are useful for evaluating the accuracy of predictive models and highlighting where models or data struggle to capture important aspects of a phenomenon.

Third, it is possible to infer detailed urban fabric types in new contexts based on data from different countries. In contrast to most other urban form models, we predict at the building level at scale. The relative difficulty of the task depends on the specific country, urban form being predicted and dataset used. Furthermore, heterogenous but more detailed data, is preferable to homogenous but coarser data, for urban morphological analysis.

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Biographies

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